

Comparative Performance of Machine Learning Models for Monthly Evaporation Prediction at Khanpur Dam

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Abstract: Accurate prediction of evaporation is critical for effective reservoir management and sustainable water resource planning. This study evaluates the performance of three machine learning models—Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Machine (SVM)—for monthly evaporation prediction at the Khanpur Dam watershed. The input variables include maximum and minimum temperature, wind speed, relative humidity, and rainfall, with data spanning 2014–2023. Model training and testing were conducted on 2014–2020 and 2021–2023 data, respectively. The results indicate that RF outperformed the other models, achieving Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) values of 0.89 (training) and 0.70 (testing), and a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.93 and 0.70. XGBoost demonstrated competitive performance, with NSE values of 0.82 and 0.66 and an R^2 of 0.87 and 0.67 for training and testing phases, respectively. Conversely, SVM showed poor predictive capability, with negative NSE values and high errors even after hyperparameter tuning.

Keywords: Evaporation, Random Forest (RF), SVM, XGBoost

1. Introduction

Evaporation is a crucial factor in controlling the hydrological cycle that is why accurate estimations of evaporation losses are crucial for water resources management, irrigation systems' design, and agricultural production planning. Furthermore, the increasing evaporation rate is another sign of global warming [1] which approves the need for tracking the rate of evaporation to implement adequate water management practices. Since evaporation causes significant water loss affecting water storages such as lakes and reservoirs and being part of total water budget, it is therefore necessary to understand and estimate evaporation losses in the context of formulating water resource management strategies [2], water resource and irrigation policy, and methods of water management for crop production.

The rate of evaporation is affected by vapor pressure difference and amount of heat available which are dependent on different climatic factors such as solar radiation intensity, humidity, wind velocity, air temperature and atmospheric pressure [3], [4]. These factors are also linked with geography, season, and climate type. Hence, evaporation is a complicated phenomenon with exceptionally non-linear properties.

Evaporation can be predicted directly or indirectly. Some estimation techniques include Energy balance method, Water balance approach, Mass transfer technique, Penman's equation besides the evaporating pans. From these, evaporation pans are popularly used based on cost efficiency and ease of maintenance [5]. However, their application depends on factors such as wind speed and vapor pressure, and its application may be limited for deployment especially in regions that are hard to reach. All indirect methods depend on weather conditions, and other physical parameters such as energy and volume conservations which could need complex measuring tools and skilled personnel. These methods are also faced with the usual drawbacks inherent to evaporation

processes, which is the high complexity and nonlinearity of the process, making it difficult to obtain data of stable quality. Due to such restrictions, researchers have focused on other strategies to enhance efficiency of evaporation estimation. In the last few years, different machine learning (ML) techniques offer promising alternatives for predicting evaporation by learning from historical data patterns [6], [7], [8]. Machine learning (ML) techniques have proven to be effective because they are capable of addressing intricate relationships with no preliminary or causal assumptions. Of them, the random forest (RF) algorithm has been extremely useful in agricultural processes including land cover classification [9], management of water resources [10] and predicting crop yield [11] tasks. One of the reasons for its wide applicability is its high precision in classification and regression tasks with low dependence on parameters, quick processing, and overfitting problem management [12]. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is another important choice by practitioners for prediction of evaporation for small to medium datasets [13]. Liu et. al [14] have employed Support Vector Machine (SVM) for evaporation prediction because of its high training efficiency.

This study aims to compare the performance of Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Machines (SVM) in predicting monthly evaporation from a time series of meteorological data at Khanpur Dam. By leveraging these machine learning models, we seek to enhance the accuracy and reliability of evaporation forecasts, which could significantly contribute to better reservoir management and water conservation strategies.

2. Study Area

The Khanpur Dam is found on the Haro River; this is approximately 50 kilometers away from Islamabad, Pakistan. The Khanpur dam is situated in the Photohar Plateau, north-west of the reservoir of the dam lies at longitudes $72^{\circ} 53' 30''$ to $73^{\circ} 26' 20''$ and latitudes $33^{\circ} 43' 40''$ to $34^{\circ} 06' 00''$, as illustrated in Figure 1. Its reservoir provides potable water for

Rawalpindi and Islamabad and irrigation water for vast of the cultivated areas and the neighbor industrial areas around the cities. The Khanpur dam watershed is located in the semi humid to humid zone of the country with temperature varying from 2.1 °C to 46.6°C.

Figure 1: Study Area Map

3. Methodology

This study focuses on predicting monthly evaporation at the Khanpur Dam watershed using machine learning models: Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The methodology flow chart is shown in Figure 2.

The dataset has been acquired from Khanpur Dam Officials spanning from 2014 to 2023. The variables include maximum temperature (Tmax), Minimum Temperature (Tmin), precipitation, wind speed, solar radiation, relative humidity, and evaporation. The data from 2014-2020 was selected as training and from 2021-2023 as testing. Before model development, the data was pre-processed involving quality check and normalizing the input variables. Afterwards, three machine learning models were implemented to predict monthly evaporation. RF is an ensemble learning ML technique that involves multiple decision trees. XGBoost is gradient boosting algorithm known for capturing non-linear relationship and SVM follows a regression approach. Grid search was applied to tune hyper parameters, and all the three models were evaluated using four statistical measures i.e. Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), percent bias (PBIAS), Coefficient of Determination (R²), and mean absolute error as represented by equations 1-4

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{obs,i} - Y_{pred,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{obs,i} - \mu_{obs})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$PBIAS = 100 \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{obs,i} - Y_{pred,i})}{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_{obs,i}} \quad (2)$$

$$R^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{obs,i} - \mu_{obs})(Y_{pred,i} - \mu_{pred})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{obs,i} - \mu_{obs})^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_{pred,i} - \mu_{pred})^2} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Methodology Flow Chart

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |Y_{obs,i} - Y_{pred,i}| \quad (4)$$

Symbol	Description
$Y_{obs,i}$	Observed values
$Y_{pred,i}$	Predicted values
μ_{obs}	Mean of observed values
μ_{pred}	Mean of predicted values
n	Number of observations

4. Results

The performance of the three machine learning models—XGBoost, RF, and SVM—was evaluated using four metrics: NSE, PBIAS, R², and MAE. Specifically, it targeted the period 2014–2020 for training, and the period from 2021 to 2023 for testing the scaling impact. Figure 3 represents scatter plots of all the three models during training and testing phase. In the case of the training dataset, RF used to train the models resulted to the highest NSE score of 0.89, R-squared of 0.93, PBIAS of -0.3 and the lowest MAE score of 1.77. XGBoost came second with an NSE of 0.82, the R² of 0.87, PBIAS of

-5.6, and MAE of 2.18. SVM, however, had a low NSE of -0.50, R^2 of 0.61, MAE of 3.10 and PBIAS of 2.88.

For the testing dataset, similar to before, better performance was observed in RF model with recorded NSE of 0.70, R^2 of 0.70 and MAE of 2.20. XGBoost ranked second with the NSE of 0.66, R^2 of 0.67 and MAE of 2.50. During the testing both models had low bias, specifically PBIAS of 1.56 for RF and -3.15 for XG Boost.

During testing, however, SVM was less effective. Reduction of its NSE values up to -0.02, making this model less accurate. Additionally, its PBIAS of -29.46 and the MAE of 4.60 indicate that there exists severe bias and relatively larger errors compared to both RF and XGBoost. The comparison between three models is depicted with the help of time series plot in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Scatter Plots during Training and Testing Phase

Qualitatively, RF was found to outperform other models for both training and testing sets, yielding highest NSE and R^2 , and at the same time lowest MAE along with least bias. Due to the ensemble nature of RF, it provides better performances than GBM which can handle non-linear relationships and also reduces the issue of over fitting. The efficacy of the three ML models as determined by the statistical indices is represented by radar plot in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Time Series Plot During Training and Testing

XGBoost also gave almost comparable performance, slightly lagging behind RF, especially on testing data set. SVM,

however, failed to give reliable results concerning evaporation. The negative NSE values along with higher errors indicate that the SVM struggled to capture the non-linearity in the data set.

Figure 5: Radar plot comparing ML methods in training and test phases

5. Discussion

This research underscores the applicability of ensembling techniques such as RF and XGBoost for accurate and reliable estimation of evaporation. These models can prove useful in formulating and implementing effective reservoir regulation techniques and where there are ongoing efforts to combat climate change.

6. Conclusions

The study assessed the predictive capabilities of three ML models i.e Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) for monthly evaporation at the Khanpur Dam watershed utilizing the available metrological variables (maximum and minimum temperature, wind speed, relative humidity and rainfall) as the predictors.

The results emphasize that RF performed better than the other models with high values of accuracy as indicated by the R^2 of 0.93 and 0.70 during training and testing, and NSE of 0.89 and 0.7 respectively and low errors as indicated by its MAE and PBIAS metrics. XGBoost also did well on the test obtaining comparable accuracy although at a somewhat lower level than RF which was more robust. The results suggest that ensemble-based models like RF are appropriate to be able to manage the complex nonlinear relationships that characterize evaporation processes. In contrast, SVM struggled to reach an acceptable level of performance, through systematic hyperparameter tuning, with negative NSE values and high errors. This indicates that the SVM approach does not contribute positively to the modeling of evaporation in situations characterized by complex interactions among many dimensions.

The study highlights the effectiveness of ensemble learning models for hydrological applications, particularly when non-linear relationships are dominant. By integrating RF or XGBoost into reservoir management practices, decision-makers can achieve more accurate evaporation predictions, enabling better water resource planning and management.

7. Recommendation

Future research work can focus on some deep learning models especially the Long Short-Term Memory networks which are well developed to understand computerized temporal patterns in time series data. In addition, extending analysis with other meteorological and hydrological parameters or using methods for combining different models might improve prediction quality.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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